

FORMS AND METHODS OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION OF CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10559970>

Abstract. Growing up of today's boys and girls is a responsible task for the life of our society and the fate of the whole Earth. That is why it is very important to educate each of them to love nature, respect all living creatures, and foresee the consequences of their actions in nature. The article talks about methods of providing environmental education to children at MTT.

Key words: education, ecology, ecological knowledge, methods, means, forms of education, ecological culture.

What is ecology? Ecology is a science that studies the relationships of living organisms with each other and with the environment. If we pay attention, today sometimes we can throw away plastic bottles and cups, ignoring the norms of simple behavior. many do, and it all happens in front of children. But we need to educate the culture of ecological behavior in preschool children, to awaken their ecological consciousness. Children's behavior is formed on the basis of ecological culture, ecological knowledge, practical skills, and aesthetic experiences. A preschool child should learn to empathize with living creatures: a living creature is hurt, it must be loved, animals cannot be harmed, we have no right to destroy what nature has created. We need to instill in children the feeling of the world around us, like a huge house in which we all live.

The main forms of ecological education:

Direct educational activity - Activity is the leading form of organizing children's introduction to nature. Excursions

- Ecological holidays and recreation
- Acquaintance of children with nature in everyday life
- Today special attention is paid to preschool education in our country.

In particular, the "First Step" state curriculum, the state educational standard of preschool education, the development and implementation of concepts of preschool education are an important part of the general

pedagogical process. As in any process, educators try to use all the teaching methods and techniques available to them. There are several forms of environmental education in preschool educational organizations. These are: Visual, practical, verbal Visual method - it is better to show once than to tell a hundred times, especially about children and their relationship with nature. Visual methods in environmental education: observations, viewing pictures, showing models, slideshow. Visual methods are fully compatible with the abilities of children's cognitive activity, allowing them to form vivid, clear ideas about nature. Practical method - games, experiments, modeling. The use of these methods allows the teacher to clarify and deepen thoughts and introduce the knowledge he has acquired into the system by establishing connections and relationships between individual objects and natural phenomena. Practical methods are very important for the full integration of children into ecological culture. 1. Modeling. The modeling method is very suitable for primary and secondary children. This is the replacement of real things (events) with the help of schemes, symbols, figures or images.

Simulation helps to give children a general understanding of the object being studied. Experiments and experiences. Experience in environmental education is the observation of the studied object in specially created conditions. The experiment must have a purpose and a purpose. It is necessary to think about the process of experimentation, as well as technologies and tools. The experience itself is logically completed orally or in writing. 3. Environmental games. Didactic, mobile, desktop or oral - the game is to know, know and reinforce the material. The game is widely used by kindergarten teachers as a method of environmental education, because the game is a leading activity of preschool age. Verbal method - stories, works of art, conversations, verbal methods help children to form a positive emotional attitude towards nature. By oral methods we mean conversations, stories, analysis of what you read or see. Verbal methods are almost always supported by visual methods. Conversation always precedes any game, experiment, observation. Any other method will accompany the conversation. One of the oral methods is reading fiction. It can be either special environmental literature recommended by the curriculum or works of classical authors. Currently, many authors are publishing their books paying attention to the problems of nature, animal world, environmental protection. The importance of games in providing environmental knowledge to children in preschool educational organizations is incomparable. In the process of didactic games, children clarify, combine and review their thoughts about

natural phenomena, plants, animals. Didactic games allow children to work with natural objects, compare them, note changes in their individual external signs. Experiment - This is an observation carried out in specially organized conditions. The experience not only helps children develop interest in nature, but also develops observation and mental activity. In each experiment, the cause of the observed phenomenon is determined, children are led to judgments and conclusions. Excursion is one of the main types of activities and a special form of organizing work on environmental education of preschool children. The advantage of excursions is that they allow children to be introduced to natural objects and phenomena in natural conditions. During excursions, children get acquainted with plants, animals, and at the same time with their living conditions, which helps to form basic ideas about relationships in nature. Excursions have a great role in the aesthetic education of children, in the formation of their aesthetic attitude to natural phenomena and objects..

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